

Exploration targeting of conduit-type orthomagmatic Ni-Cu-PGE-Co deposits in northern Finland.

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Metals such as nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), and platinum group metals (PGMs) have a wide range of significant uses in modern, green industries. However, their current supply levels are insufficient to meet the projected demand. Therefore, these metals are considered "critical raw materials" and are of strategic importance. Local production of these materials is critical due to their significance in industrial value chains and green sectors. The SEMACRET project is dedicated to promoting sustainable exploration of (critical) raw materials within the EU to ensure a consistent supply during the green energy transition.

This article describes a computer-based prospectivity analysis of conduit-type, sulphide-rich Ni-Cu-(PGM)-(Co) deposits in northern Finland using Fuzzy Inference Systems (FIS), a supervised, knowledge-based symbolic artificial intelligence technique; and Self Organising Maps (SOM), a neural network-based unsupervised machine learning clustering algorithm.

The supervised approach relies on a generalised conceptual mineral systems model for conduit-type sulphide deposits, which is used to identify the targeting criteria. The major components of the mineral systems include (1) Primitive, mantle-derived, magnesium-rich rocks (ultramafic and mafic rocks), which are the primary source of metal; (2) trans-lithospheric faults and chonoliths that serve as pathways of magma, locally enhanced by varying compressional/extensional tectonic regimes; and (3) dilatational zones of high, fracture-related permeability and localised structures that act as physical traps; along with abundant sulphur-rich crustal rocks that can provide the external sulphur required to form immiscible sulphide melts. The targeting criteria were represented by their spatial proxies in the form of GIS predictor maps, derived using spatial analyses and geoprocessing tools. These predictor maps were integrated in a multi-stage FIS structured on the mineral systems model to obtain the prospectivity map.

To complement the results of the knowledge-driven analysis and eliminate any subjective bias in the manual processing and filtering involved in the generation of predictor maps, SOM was applied to unprocessed gridded geophysical, geochemical and topographic datasets to cluster features representative of the mineralisation processes in an automated and unsupervised manner. The results of the two approaches were comparable.

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